

Assessing inter-basin groundwater input to the Verlorenvlei estuarine lake using stable isotopes and hydrochemistry

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ABSTRACT

Study region: Verlorenvlei Catchment (~1 890 km²) is an agriculture-dominated area (~43 % per km²) on South Africa's west coast. This semi-arid region has variable rainfall and high evaporation rates, affecting the three major aquifers and Verlorenvlei – a RAMSAR-listed estuarine lake.

Study focus: Natural processes (i.e., extended dry periods and evaporation) and anthropogenic activities (i.e., agricultural expansion and groundwater abstraction) have threatened Verlorenvlei's ecological functions. Seasonal and spatial changes between the water sources (i.e., direct rainfall, surface water, and groundwater) supporting Verlorenvlei were determined using $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ isotopes and hydrochemical analyses. Inter-basin aquifer contribution was investigated to assist in explaining Verlorenvlei's slow recovery since the recent 2015 – 2018 Western Cape drought. **New insights:** A proportion of groundwater from outside the topographic and surface-water delineated catchment supports Verlorenvlei during the dry month of April (i.e., G30F Langvlei sub-catchment). Furthermore, Verlorenvlei experiences high evaporation (evaporation best fit line: $\delta^2\text{H} = 12.49 \times \delta^{18}\text{O} - 47.68$, average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of 47.1 ‰ and average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of 7.64 ‰) compared to its feeding rivers. Two sandstone and shale-dominated sub-catchments exhibit overlapping groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values and water types to the sub-catchment in the nearest vicinity of Verlorenvlei, suggesting a disproportionately high groundwater contribution from these sub-catchments to Verlorenvlei. Evaluation of Verlorenvlei's water balance should consider both surface water and groundwater sources, particularly from inter-basin aquifer sources during prolonged droughts.

1. Introduction

Climate change is causing significant variations in local, regional, and global atmospheric temperature, evaporation rates, as well as rainfall intensity and frequency, leading to concomitant changes in the hydrological cycle (IPCC, 2007). To adapt to these changes, the world's population has been increasing its reliance on groundwater (Scanlon et al., 2023). From 1960 – 2010, groundwater abstraction globally increased from ~350 km³/yr to ~1 000 km³/yr, which was notably connected to the increase in irrigated regions

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of India, Northern Iran, Pakistan, Nile, and China (Wada and Bierkens, 2014). The increase in groundwater use globally has led to significant declines in groundwater levels. Consequently, this affects the flux between surface water and groundwater systems and the associated sustainability of groundwater withdrawals from these systems (Barlow and Leake, 2012; Burkett and Kusler, 2000; Hilton and Jasechko, 2023). Mitigating these impacts and developing effective adaptation strategies to climate change requires a detailed understanding of catchment hydrological dynamics.

Watershed or catchment delineation is the first key step in understanding a catchment's water budget and its potential response to climate change and anthropogenic stresses. Natural processes affecting the water balance include erosion and concentrated flooding. In KwaZulu-Natal, flood episodes lead to the linkage of the uMfolozi River and St. Lucia Lake, hence seasonally changing their river and estuarine morphology, sediment flux, water quality, and soil water storage (Cooper et al., 1990; Pillay et al., 2003; 2014). Anthropogenic factors influencing the water budget involve; reservoir construction, channelization, river diversions, intense irrigation, wastewater treatment plant effluent, and groundwater abstraction (Alizade Govarchin Ghale et al., 2018; Archer et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023; Xin and Kinouchi, 2013). Between 1998 – 2010, the water level decline of the Urmia Lake in Iran was believed to be caused by drought conditions (Alizade Govarchin Ghale et al., 2018). However, anthropogenic processes (i.e., damming, abstraction, and water-consuming agriculture practices) are responsible for 80 % of the Urmia Lakes shrinkage. When hydrological systems change, by

Fig. 1. (a) Location of the Verlorenvlei Catchment (red square), De Mond/Heuningnes and Lake St Lucia estuaries (orange squares) in the Western Cape of South Africa; (b) The Verlorenvlei Catchment positioned between the Swartberge, Olifants River, and Piketberg mountains with the Verlorenvlei RAMSAR-listed estuarine lake (light blue) and its supporting tributaries.

both natural processes and anthropogenic activities, so does our understanding of what a catchment's water budget represents and how it should be delineated. Determining this is important in water-stressed environments to ensure harmonious environmental and socio-economic water management (Allan et al., 2020; Dai et al., 2004, 2018; Ndebele et al., 2020, IPCC, 2007; Seward, 2010; Woodhouse and Muller, 2017).

Hydrologists typically delineate catchment boundaries and river networks based on Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) software packages such as ArcHydro or GRASS-Hydrological Response Unit (HRU) (Arnold et al., 1998; Fink et al., 2007; Flügel, 1995; Krause, 2001, 2002; Nepal et al., 2014; Schwartz, 2008). Next, the DEMs are incorporated into modelling packages and used to identify homogenous hydrological response regions at reduced expense, errors, and processing time, compared to manually tracing watershed boundaries from topographic maps or DEMs (Amir et al., 2014). The implicit assumption here is that the catchment boundaries can be defined only by the surface water system. However, the assumption that the aquifer water table follows topography has been tested and found to be poorly correlated, particularly in highly permeable aquifers with relatively low recharge rates (Desbarats et al., 2002; Haitjema, 1995; Haitjema and Mitchell-Bruker, 2005; Moore and Thompson, 1996; Muller, 2012; Ostrom, 2010; Shaman et al., 2002; Winter et al., 2003). Consequently, applying this assumption when developing water balance models can lead to incorrect water budgets and unsustainable water management plans (Hammond and Han, 2006; Le Moine et al., 2007; Pilgrim et al., 1988).

Watershed delineations need to account for all water contributing to the catchment water budget, including runoff, interflow, as well as local and regional baseflow. This necessitates identifying the groundwater boundary, dominant flow paths, residence times, and the proportion of sub-catchment contributions, to fully characterize the catchment hydrological system. Groundwater divides fluctuate vertically and laterally due to the seasonal water level change from precipitation (dominant recharge source), groundwater-surface water interactions, and anthropogenic influence (e.g., groundwater abstraction) resulting in variable sources of groundwater inflow spatially and temporally (Holzbecher, 2001; Savage, 2005; Winter et al., 2003). A rise in the water table would increase the catchment groundwater availability for streamflow and abstraction, and vice-versa for a lowered groundwater boundary (Smith et al., 2018). Shifts in the subsurface water divide influence the groundwater flow path direction and rate, in turn affecting the groundwater proportional contribution from each respective sub-catchment. As a result, the spatial distributional changes in groundwater impact the water budget. Additionally, an aquifer system is not one homogenous unit, but consists of different hydraulic conductivities (K) and groundwater flow paths of different residence times superimposed on one another from different sources (i.e., local, intermediate, and regional flow paths) (Winter et al., 2003). Accounting for K-values and short/long residence times is important as the rock-water interaction contact time influences the water quality (Holzbecher, 2001).

Identifying the aforementioned factors is fundamental to constraining the spatial and temporal groundwater boundary conditions of a catchment in hydrological models. This ultimately improves the accuracy of the water budget, which leads to more sustainable groundwater management plans (Linhares et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2022; Yeh et al., 2014). Water stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$) are a reliable method to constrain catchment boundaries, source contribution, and water budget, particularly for data-poor catchments in water-scarce regions. Water stable isotopes can be collected through simple sampling processes and their ratios can be analyzed with high precision (Kerstel and Gianfrani, 2008; Koehler et al., 2013; Mazurenka et al., 2005; Tweed, 2019). Furthermore, the complimentary use of major ions with O and H isotopes can define water types and the mixing relationship of interconnected aquifers, to implement effective groundwater management strategies (Kumar, 2013; Wolf et al., 2007). By integrating these methods, a catchment's total water budget can be determined at a higher level of confidence by creating rainfall-runoff model that accounts for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values, thereby considering evaporation and water source mixing (Birkel and Soulsby, 2015; Dansgaard, 1964; Stadnyk et al., 2013; Tsujimura et al., 2007; Wallace, 2021; Watson et al., 2023). This application will prove beneficial as forecasted drier climate heightens groundwater reliance, as an adaptive measure, especially during droughts in semi-arid environments.

The Verlorenvlei, listed under the wetlands Ramsar Convention, is a coastal estuarine lake located in a semi-arid region on the west coast of South Africa (Fig. 1) (Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, 2018). The estuarine lake is ranked as one of the top ten South African estuaries for the prime conservation of waterbirds based on its high index score for species richness, conservation value, and status; however, it is threatened (Turpie, 1995; Water Research Commission, 2011). Over time the water quality and quantity supporting the estuarine lake have declined due to variable rainfall (~300 mm/yr), high potential evaporation rates (1 800 – 2 400 mm/yr), and land-use changes (CSIR, 2009; Eilers et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2017, 2020). The groundwater systems were under pressure during the 2015 – 2018 Western Cape (WC) drought and the recent 2020 – 2021 dry seasons, causing an increase in groundwater dependence (Watson et al., 2020; Wolski et al., 2020; Nenweli et al., 2024; Wolski, 2018). Furthermore, Verlorenvlei water levels prior to the 2023 wet season had not recovered fully (Fig. 2). This changed the hydrology of the lake system and impacted its biodiversity (Miller et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2020).

The extremely low water levels in the estuarine lake (recorded as recently as March 2023) and its recovery have not been fully explained through existing hydrological models, climate records, groundwater residence times, and mixing relationships (Watson et al., 2018, 2020, Miller et al., 2022). In this study, we investigate seasonal changes and spatial contribution of the water sources (e.g., direct rainfall, surface water, and groundwater) by analysing $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ isotopes and hydrochemistry. Findings have assisted in explaining the hydrogeological dynamics of the areas supporting Verlorenvlei, particularly during the dry year of 2022. Additionally, insights into the different water sources' interconnectivity can assist in explaining Verlorenvlei's slow recovery. This study's simple field and analysis approach enables a rapid and cost-effective assessment of seasonal and spatial hydrological processes both within and outside a catchment (e.g., identify dominant contributing sub-catchments and inter-basin aquifer flow). These methods are applicable to other catchments in semi-arid areas with limited water resource monitoring, providing valuable insights to support sustainable water management strategies in areas facing similar prolonged droughts.

(caption on next page)

Fig. 2. Verlorenvlei estuarine lake water levels (dashed black lines) timelapse from 2004 to 2022: (a) 10/2004, (b) 11/2005, (c) 11/2012, (d) 03/2018, (e) 04/2021, and (f) 04/2022. (g) Verlorenvlei's Catchment mean annual rainfall (black bar) according to farmers and the Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management 2023 records (Muche et al., 2018) (supplementary material Table S1). Red-outlined black bars correlate with the annual rainfall of the years when the images were captured. Bars are equal to the sum of each rain gauge and rain automated weather station rainfall volume per sub-catchment area-weighted contribution: $\sum_{i=1}^n R_{SC-RG/RS} * W_{sc}$, where; n = number of rain stations, SC-RG/RS = sub-catchment rain gauge or rain station, R = annual rainfall (mm) according to records from farmers' rain gauges and rain stations, and W = ratio of the sub-catchment area (km²) to the Verlorenvlei catchment area (km²).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

The Verlorenvlei estuarine lake is one of South Africa's largest at ~19 km² and is periodically disconnected from the ocean due to a sandbar, except during floods (CSIR, 2009; Miller et al., 2022). The lake sits within the Verlorenvlei Catchment (~1 890 km²), positioned in the Sandveld region of the WC (3224°S; 1826°E) (Fig. 1). It is confined to the east and north-east by the Swartberg (~1 300 m above sea level (m.a.s.l.)) and Olifantsriver (~990 m.a.s.l.) mountains and the west and south-west by the Piketberg Mountains (1 446 m.a.s.l.), extending to the coast at Elands Bay. The Verlorenvlei has previously hosted fourteen fish species and waterfowl including egrets, great white pelicans, black-crowned night herons, Cape teals, reed cormorants, and flamingos (Archer et al., 2009; Turpie, 1995). Notably, flamingos rely on the Verlorenvlei when the northern Wadrifoutpan and Rocher Pan wetlands are dry (Barnes, 2000; Collar et al., 1996; Sinclair et al., 1986). The vegetation transitions from Fynbos inland to Strandveld (semi-succulent beach vegetation) on the western coastline plains (Acocks, 1988; CSIR, 2009). The predominant crops cultivated are potatoes, table grapes, and citrus (i.e., lemons, nartjies, and oranges), with the total irrigated sectors occupying 81 621 ha of the catchment between 2015 – 2021 (GeoTerraImage, 2015; Umvoto, 2021; Water Research Commission, 2011).

Sub-catchments are indicated with the following letters: [G30D] Krom Antonies; [G30D] Hol; [G30B] Kruismans; [G30C] Bergvallei; [G30E] Verloren, and [G30E] Papakuil. Langvlei sub-catchment [G30F] is located outside of the Verlorenvlei delineated watershed. The confluence is the point where all tributaries contribute to Verlorenvlei (yellow star).

Four major lithological units characterize the catchments geology. The oldest rock unit is the Neoproterozoic (542 – 750 Ma) Malmesbury Group (MG) and is represented by the Piketberg Formation consisting of limestone, phyllitic greywacke, conglomerate, sericite schist, and quartzite (Conrad et al., 2004; Rozendaal et al., 1994). At the base of the Piketberg Mountains, the MG unit has been intruded by the Riviera Granite pluton of the Cambrian (495 – 545 Ma) Cape Granite Suite (CGS) (Kisters et al., 2015; Rozendaal et al., 1994; Rust, 1967). Unconformably overlying these two major formations are the quartzose sandstones of the Palaeozoic (354 – 444 Ma) Table Mountain Group (TMG), which aligns with the eastern ridge of the catchment (Johnson et al., 2006). Within the catchment, the TMG dominates the mountainous regions and consists of the Piekenierskloof, Graafwater, Peninsula, Cederberg, and Nardouw Formations (Conrad et al., 2004; Johnson et al., 2006; Rust, 1967; Sigidi et al., 2017). The Peninsula Formation outcrops at the top of the Piketberg and Swartberge mountains. Quaternary (0 – 2 Ma) alluvial sediments of the Sandveld Group extend from the coast of False Bay to Elands Bay along the valley floors (3 – 12 m thick) (Conrad et al., 2004; Roberts et al., 2006).

Verlorenvlei Catchments three major hydrostratigraphic units are: (1) the Quaternary unconsolidated primary Alluvial Aquifer, made up of coarse-grained sands producing relatively high-yielding boreholes; (2) the MG semiconfined to confined secondary aquifer of fractured shale; and (3) the TMG fractured rock aquifer composed of sandstone and quartzite, located on the catchment mountain ranges (Eilers et al., 2017; Conrad et al., 2004; CSIR, 2009). The primary and secondary aquifers are presumed to be separated by a partial clay aquitard dominantly present in the lower valley region (Conrad et al., 2004). This clay layer varies in thickness from 3 – 25 m with possible windows and discontinuities. Fracture networks in the Peninsula Formation are exposed on the mountain tops and contribute recharge to the valley aquifers, as the mountains create a high hydraulic gradient (Conrad et al., 2004; Münch et al., 2013; Timmerman, 1985; Watson et al., 2018). A predominant NW-SE groundwater flow direction within the catchment is thought to be controlled by bedding planes, weathering zones, and faults (Conrad et al., 2004). Two major NW-SE trending faults in the Verlorenvlei Catchment are the Piketberg-Wellington and Redelinghuys faults (De Beer, 2003), both of which are thought to be important water transport features. Additionally, the Alluvial Aquifer flow direction coincides with the surface water tributaries and topography (GEOSS, 2006).

The Verlorenvlei Catchment was delineated using the Hydrological Response Unit (HRU – defines regions of homogenous topographical and physiological properties) delineation tool followed by an automated AML (ArcMarkup Language) tool in ArcMap (Pfennig et al., 2009; Watson et al., 2019). Before delineation, the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) 90 m digital elevation model was used to fill in the data gaps (i.e., sink artificial features) using the standard fill algorithm from ArcInfo (Jenson and Domingue, 1988).

The estuarine lake is supported by surface runoff and groundwater flow composed of both fresh and saline water (Conrad et al., 1999; Miller et al., 2022). The four tributaries supporting Verlorenvlei are the Bergvallei, Kruismans, Krom Antonies, and Hol, which feed into the Verloren River which flows westwards into the estuarine lake (Fig. 1). Rivers predominantly flow in winter and early summer with trickle flows during dry summer months (Sinclair, 1986). Precipitation decreases from 370 – 785 mm/yr in the Piketberg Mountains to 210 mm/yr in the west at Elands Bay (Lynch, 2004) (Fig. 2). Simulated evaporation, based on the J2000 rainfall/runoff model, increases towards the coastline with rates of 950 mm/yr in the upper Krom Antonies and 1 460 mm/yr at the intersection of the Krom Antonies and Hol River, a location termed the confluence (Fig. 1) (Watson et al., 2018). The confluence represents the point of

accumulation of all tributaries into the Verloren River.

2.2. Methodology

In total, 168 cumulative daily rainfall (6 May to 21 December 2022), 18 surface water, and 104 groundwater samples were collected in February (dry season), April (dry season), and June (wet season) 2022. Table 1 and Fig. 3 indicate the distribution and frequency of rainwater, surface water, and groundwater samples collected per sampling campaign. A cumulative daily rainfall sample represents the total rainfall over 24 hours from 08:00. Surface water was taken from major tributaries when the rivers were flowing. Additionally, the Verlorenvlei Catchments annual rainfall between 2000 – 2021 was recorded based on twelve farmers' long-term rainfall records and one of 2023 automated weather stations (Muche et al., 2018) (supplementary material Table S1). Groundwater was collected from the Alluvial, MG, and TMG aquifers across and outside the delineated watershed. The borehole depths were recorded (supplementary material Table S5 and S6); however, the screen depths were not known. It is assumed the sampled groundwater signifies a single aquifer being intersected at the depth of collection (Miller et al., 2022). However, boreholes at different locations may intersect different aquifers. Water samples for major ions and H and O stable isotopes were filtered through 0.22 µm Nylon and Cellulose Acetate (CA) filters, respectively, using a 50 mL clean syringe into a clean 50 mL polypropylene (PP) falcon tube and 15 mL PP falcon tube, respectively. Next, the samples were stored below 4°C until analysis. Cation samples were pre-acidified with 0.5 mL of 1 M ultrapure nitric acid to inhibit the precipitation of metals. Field measurements using a portable ExStik EXTECH EC500 pH/conductivity meter included electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, and temperature.

Anions and cations concentrations were measured using a Metrohm Ion Chromatogram (IC) 930 and an Agilent 7700 Inductivity Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), respectively, in the Central Analytical Facility at Stellenbosch University. Total alkalinity levels (mgCaCO₃/L) were measured by the Skalar BluVision™ Discrete Nutrient Analysis (DA), and are equivalent to the samples bicarbonate alkalinity (HCO₃ - in mg/L). The average charge balance (CB) for groundwater and surface water were within the acceptable range with a value of 9 %

(Murray and Wade, 1996). Overall, the analytical procedure accuracy was 71 % acceptable (CB: ~10 %), of which 46 % was accurate (CB: ~5 %). Total alkalinity and major ions analyses commenced within 3 – 5 days after sample collection.

Oxygen and hydrogen stable isotopes were measured using a laser Cavity Ring Down Spectroscopy (CRDS) on a Los Gatos Research (LGR) GLA431-Triple Liquid Water Isotope Analyser (LGR T-LWIA) utilizing Off-Axis Integrated-Cavity Output Spectroscopy (OA-ICOS) instrument at Stellenbosch University's Biogeochemistry Research Infrastructure Platform (BIOGRIP) Soil and Water Node. Standard LGR T-LWIA operations and data processing procedures were followed according to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), (2009) and the Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) for Lasers 2015 (Coplen and Wassenaar, 2015; Wassenaar et al., 2014). Prior to starting the run, the system is primed with deionized water. In a single run the laboratory LGR working standard (LGR 1D or LGR 2D – lower δ¹⁸O and δ²H ratios) and laboratory in-house standard (BIHS3 - higher δ¹⁸O and δ²H ratios) are analysed, followed by 10 samples and two calibrated Quality Controls (QCs: BIHS1 and BIHS2) samples. LGR 1D and LGR 2D were calibrated against the Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water 2 (VSMOW2) and SLAP (Standard Light Antarctic Precipitation) waters. BIHS1, BIHS2, and BIHS3 were calibrated against the United States Geological Survey (USGS) 48 and USGS53 waters.

To account for the memory effect each sample is auto-sampled nine times with the last five injections averaged to obtain the average ¹⁸O/¹⁶O and ²H/¹H ratios. Next, the ¹⁸O/¹⁶O and ²H/¹H average ratios were bracketed normalized using the IAEA LIMS for Lasers software (Coplen and Wassenaar, 2015). LGR T-LWIA analytical precision/uncertainty was ±0.15 ‰ and ±0.5 ‰ for δ¹⁸O and δ²H, respectively. Precision (repeatability) is the average standard deviation of the repeated QC injections, expressed as one standard deviation (1-σ) from the mean value. The overall sample run performance was acceptable with an average standard deviation of 0.08 ‰ and 0.5 ‰ for δ¹⁸O and δ²H, respectively (Coplen and Wassenaar, 2015). Additionally, an outlier analysis was performed on the rainwater δ¹⁸O and δ²H values. Oxygen and hydrogen stable isotope analyses commenced within 3 – 5 days after sample collection.

Table 1

The cumulative rainfall volume and the number of cumulative daily rainfall, surface water, and groundwater samples collected from each sub-catchment during 2022. According to the Southern African Science Services Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management, the Eagles Pride Weather Station (Station ID: 511944) installed in Piketberg Mountain recorded 26 missing rainfall events (i.e., a rainwater event >2 mm, but no sample was collected) from 6 May to 21 December 2022.

Sub-catchment	Cumulative Rainfall (mm)	No. of Cumulative Daily Rainfall Samples								No. of Surface Water Samples			No. of Boreholes Samples		
		May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Feb	Apr	Jun	Feb	Apr	Jun
Verloren	95	6	12	8	9	2	0	0	2	4	/	/	8	8	8
Kruismans	273	2	4	2	7	3	0	1	4	/	/	/	2	5	4
Bo-Piketberg	251	2	3	5	3	1	0	0	1	/	/	/	3	/	9
Bergvallei	233	3	4	4	4	1	0	1	2	/	1	2	3	8	10
Hol	221	4	5	5	6	1	0	2	3	2	1	1	2	8	8
Krom Antonies	152	6	6	12	13	3	0	2	4	/	/	2	7	8	5
Langvlei	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	2	/
Wetland	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	3	1	1	/	/	/

* / = no sample collection

* 0 = no rainfall events recorded (0 mm)

Fig. 3. Location of the rainfall gauges/stations (triangle), surface water (square), and groundwater (circle) sample sites for each sub-catchment during 2022: a) Verloren, b) Langvlei, c) Bergvallei, d) Hol and Krom Antonies, e) Kruismans, and f) Bo-Piketberg.

Fig. 4. The Verlorenvlei Catchment annual rainfall between 2000 – 2021 according to farmers and 2023 records (supplementary material Table S1). High (grey region) and low (red region) rainfall years correspond with extreme La Niña (negative sea surface temperature (SST)) and El Niño (positive SST) Southern Oscillation cycles. The Oceanic Niño Index (ONI - dashed black line) measures the SST (dashed black line) anomaly relative to 0°C (red line) (L'Heureux, 2016). Verlorenvlei Catchments annual weighted rainfall (mm) (dark line) is equal to the sum of the rainfall area-weight contribution per sub-catchment: $\sum_{i=1}^n R_{SC} * W_{SC}$ - where; n = number of sub-catchments, SC = sub-catchment, R = sub-catchment annual rainfall (mm), and W = $\delta^{18}O$ and δ^2H value of the sub-catchment area (km^2) to the Verlorenvlei Catchment area (km^2).

3. Results

3.1. Rainwater

The Verlorenvlei Catchments annual rainfall input between 2000 – 2021 ranges from ~278 mm to ~880 mm, with an average rainfall of ~482 mm/yr (Fig. 4). These rainwater volumes are based on twelve farmers' rainfall records and one of 2023 automated weather station (Muche et al., 2018) (refer to supplementary material Table S1). Farmers in the Verloren and Hol sub-catchments could not provide rainfall records before 2009 and 2001, respectively. The heavy rainfall years of 2001, 2008, and 2013 ranged from ~711 mm/yr to ~880 mm/yr. During the 2015 – 2018 WC drought (Wolski, 2018; Wolski et al., 2020), the rainfall average was ~399 mm/yr and three years post-drought the rainfall average was ~483 mm/yr. The 2022 rainfall sampling period cumulative daily volume ranged from 95 mm to 273 mm (Table 1).

For the rainfall outlier criteria analysis, rainfall with positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values associated with <5 mm rainfall were accepted, as rainwater with a smaller volume is likely influenced by sub-cloud evaporation under warm conditions (Dansgaard, 1964; Crawford et al., 2017). If positive rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values were associated with >5 mm rainfall it was assumed that these water samples were stored improperly (e.g., not refrigerated), producing higher positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values than typically expected. Based on this criterion, 22 rainwater samples were removed from the dataset, leaving a total of 168 samples for data interpretation (supplementary Table S2). The 2022 Meteoric Water Line (MWL) for the Verlorenvlei Catchment is defined as $\delta^2\text{H} = 6.31 \times \delta^{18}\text{O} + 12.98$ (Figs. 5 and 6). The catchments rainfall amount-weighted average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values range from -3.29‰ to -3.82‰–3.82‰ and average $\delta^2\text{H}$ values range from -8.3‰ to -11.6‰ (Table 2). During the wet season, rainwater has lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values with a maximum deuterium (d) excess of +36.77‰ (d-excess = $\delta^2\text{H} - 8 \times \delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Dansgaard, 1964)). Deuterium excess defines the moisture conditions of the rainwater origin, whereby a positive d-excess value indicates rainfall of a lower relative humidity origin (Froehlich et al., 2002).

3.2. Surface water

Winter surface waters $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (-3.62‰ to +6.94‰) and $\delta^2\text{H}$ (-15.8‰ to +37.6‰) values aligned closer with rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values compared to summer surface waters ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$: -2.22‰ to +10.01‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$: -2.4‰ to +58.4‰) (Fig. 5). Verlorenvlei estuarine lake in summer had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of +7.81‰ and an average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of +50.9‰. In autumn, the estuarine lake had a $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of +8.16‰ and a $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of +52.9‰. In winter, the estuarine lake had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of +6.94‰ and +37.6‰, respectively. Verloren, Hol, Krom Antonies, and Bergvallei surface waters' average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are as follows: $\delta^{18}\text{O} = +3.28‰$ and $\delta^2\text{H} = +25.8‰$, $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -1.12‰$ and $\delta^2\text{H} = +0.4‰$, $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -3.46‰$ and $\delta^2\text{H} = -12.4‰$, and $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -3.73‰$ and $\delta^2\text{H} = +13.0‰$, respectively (Table 3).

The Hol ($\delta^2\text{H} = 4.89 \times \delta^{18}\text{O} + 6.45$, $n = 4$) and Verloren ($\delta^2\text{H} = 4.77 \times \delta^{18}\text{O} + 10.10$, $n = 4$) rivers showed a strong evaporation best fit line (Fig. 5). Evaporation is indicated by positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values deviating right of the MWL, as the lighter ^1H and ^{16}O isotopes preferentially evaporate first (Clark and Fritz, 2013; Craig, 1961; Dansgaard, 1964; Gat, 1996). Surface water salinity levels increased as follows: Krom Antonies < Bergvallei < Hol < Verloren < Verlorenvlei. Verlorens surface water average concentrations for Na^+ and Cl^- are 593 mg/L and 1 230 mg/L, respectively (Table 3). Verlorenvlei's average concentrations for Na^+ and Cl^- are 2 506 mg/L and 5 513 mg/L, respectively. Overall, surface water and groundwater hydrochemistry showed minor variation during the year, with the following dominant anions and cations: $\text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^- > \text{PO}_4^{3-}$ and $\text{Na}^+ > \text{Ca}^{+2} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$, respectively.

3.3. Groundwater

Summer groundwaters $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values were between -2.96‰ to -0.89‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values were between -6.7‰ to +8.5‰ (average d-excess = 16.41‰) (Fig. 6). Winter groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values range from -4.07‰ to -1.36‰ and -19.2‰ to -7.4‰ (average d-excess = +12.45‰), respectively, with majority plotted below the MWL. In summer, similar groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values occurred in the catchments northern regions between the Bergvallei sub-catchment upper reaches (BERG001: $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -2.78‰

Table 2

Rainfall $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ amount-weighted average values of the Verlorenvlei Catchment. Complete rainwater $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ dataset in Table S2 of the supplementary material.

Rain Station	$\delta^2\text{H}$ Rainfall Amount-Weighted Average (‰)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Rainfall Amount-Weighted Average (‰)
Bo-Piketberg (BOP-R1)	-10.4	-3.82
Krom Antonies (KA-R1 & KA-R2)	-8.9	-3.29
Upper (KA-R2)	-10.8	-3.50
Middle (KA-R1)	-7.2	-3.10
Hol (HOL-R1)	-10.3	-3.66
Kruismans (KRM-R1)	-11.6	-3.39
Bergvallei (BERG-R1)	-11.4	-3.66
Verloren (VER-R1 & VER-R2)	-8.3	-3.82
Elands Bay (VER-R1)	-4.2	-2.88
Redelinghuys (VER-R2)	-10.7	-4.37
Catchment	-10.2	-3.58

Fig. 5. Surface waters $\delta^2\text{H}$ vs $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ plot of the Verlorenvlei Catchment indicating the 2022 average $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values per sub-catchment (symbol colour) per season (symbol shape). Rainfall H and O stable isotope ratios = small transparent black triangles. Horizontal and vertical box plots illustrate February (F), April (A), and June (J) groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values, respectively.

and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -5.1‰) and the Kruismans sub-catchment lower reaches (KRM001 and KRM002: average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -2.81‰ and average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -5.1‰) (Fig. 6). In winter, the Kruismans sub-catchment upper reach and Bo-Piketberg sub-catchment groundwaters had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values together of -3.44‰ and -12.8‰ , respectively (supplementary material Table S6).

Groundwaters in the Bo-Piketberg sub-catchment (Fig. 3f) had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -2.75‰ and an average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -5.7‰ . These values were similar to those in the Krom Antonies sub-catchment where groundwater had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -2.82‰ and an average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -6.5‰ (Table 3). Kruismans sub-catchment upper reach groundwater average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values overlap with Krom Antonies sub-catchment middle and lower reach groundwater average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of -3.60‰ and -9.0‰ , respectively, during April (Table S6). In winter, groundwater from the upper reaches of the Krom Antonies sub-catchment had $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values that coincided with those of groundwater from the Bo-Piketberg sub-catchment and the upper reaches of the Hol sub-catchment (average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.13‰ and average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -12.4‰). Furthermore, in April, the Krom Antonies sub-catchment and the confluence groundwaters $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values overlapped (Krom Antonies: average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.31‰ and average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -8.8‰ (Table S6); Confluence - HOL101: $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.51‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -5.7‰ (Table S5)). Verloren sub-catchment groundwater average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are in close range to Bo-Piketberg and Krom Antonies sub-catchments groundwater average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (Table 3), followed by Hol sub-catchment lower reach groundwater (Table S6).

The sub-catchments groundwaters salinity increases in the following order: Bo-Piketberg < Kruismans < Bergvallei < Hol \approx Verloren < Krom Antonies (Fig. 7).

Bo-Piketberg, Kruismans, and Bergvallei sub-catchments TMG Aquifer groundwaters are freshwaters dominated by Na^+ and Cl^- ions with low concentrations. Krom Antonies sub-catchment groundwater transitions from Na-Cl to Ca-Na-Cl water type traversing downstream. The catchments MG Aquifer groundwater chemistry is distinguished as Ca-Na-Cl type before the confluence and Na-Cl type after the confluence (Verloren sub-catchment groundwater), with an increase in salinity downstream. Similar groundwater chemistry dominated by Na-Cl type occurs in groundwaters northward outside the catchment boundary, Langvlei sub-catchment (G30F), and the Verloren sub-catchment. Langvlei sub-catchment groundwater has an average Na^+ concentration of 99 mg/L and Cl^- concentration of 246 mg/L . The Verloren sub-catchment groundwater has an average Na^+ concentration of 87 mg/L and Cl^- concentration of 216 mg/L (Table 3). Furthermore, in April, the Langvlei sub-catchment groundwater had an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.46‰ and an average $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -9.5‰ (VER106 and VER107), falling within Verloren's groundwater O and H stable isotope ratio range ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of -2.72‰ to -3.57‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of -0.7‰ to -15.0‰) (Fig. 6 and Table S5). Sample VER107 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.32‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -6.3‰) has a similar groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values to VER101 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.18‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of

Table 3

Verlorenvlei Catchment arithmetic average hydrochemistry concentrations and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of surface water and groundwater in 2022. Refer to Tables S3 and S4 of the supplementary material for the surface water complete and summary datasets, respectively. Refer to Tables S5 and S6 of the supplementary material for the groundwater complete and summary datasets, respectively.

Water Type	Sub-catchment	EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	pH	TDS (mg/L)	Na ⁺ (mg/L)	K ⁺ (mg/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	$\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)	d-excess (‰)	Borehole Depth Average (m)	Host Rock & Aquifer
Surface Water	Bergvallei	347	5.87	185	26	1	6	30	98	11	9	<0.1	5	-13.0	-3.73	+16.9		
	Krom Antonies	95	7.53	50	11	<LOQ	2	1	23	5	8	<0.1	0	-12.4	-3.46	+15.28		
	Hol	915	7.18	519	96	3	22	32	280	36	49	0	3	+0.4	-1.12	+9.29		
	Verloren	3787	7.15	2573	593	9	172	128	1230	151	97	0	258	+25.8	+3.28	-0.52		
	Wetland	17967	2.94	13702	2506	59	628	726	5513	4060	2	<0.1	625	+47.1	+7.64	-13.98		
Groundwater	Bo-Piketberg	177	4.76	120	39	2	8	8	93	12	6	<0.1	28	-5.7	-2.75	+16.32	79	TMG (T)
	Bergvallei	578	4.44	334	86	2	17	17	161	24	6	0	20	-11.4	-3.42	+15.99	107	TMG (T)
	Kruismans	801	6.81	510	100	3	17	13	229	16	62	0	88	-10.5	-3.29	+15.82	62	TMG (T) & MG (S)
	Krom Antonies	1409	6.86	919	112	3	34	65	322	132	116	<0.1	216	-6.5	-2.82	+16.08	91	MG (S)
	Hol	705	6.16	463	95	2	22	28	243	23	45	0	8	-9.0	-2.98	+14.85	111	TMG (T), MG (S) & Spring
	Langvlei	862	5.23	445	99	2	19	12	246	23	7	<0.1	36	-9.5	-3.46	+18.16	/	TMG (T)
	Verloren	767	5.34	488	87	2	17	18	216	44	10	0	94	-5.8	-2.53	+14.45	37	MG (S) & Alluvial (P)

*It is assumed the sampled groundwater signifies a single aquifer being intersected at the depth of collection (Miller et al., 2022)

* / = not measured

*Charge balance measured within 10 %

*<LOQ: Below limit of quantification

*Aquifer Type: (P) = primary and (S) = secondary

Fig. 6. Groundwater $\delta^2\text{H}$ vs $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ plot of the Verlorenvlei Catchment in 2022. Horizontal and vertical box plots illustrate February (F), April (A), and June (J) groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values, respectively.

Fig. 7. Verlorenvlei Catchments groundwater and estuarine lake average hydrochemistry spatial distribution during 2022. Groundwater salinity increases as follows: Bo-Piketberg (dark blue) < Kruismans (yellow) < Bergvallei (turquoise) < Hol (grey) \cong Verloren (green) < Krom Antonies (orange). The MG Aquifer groundwaters before the confluence are Ca-Na-Cl water type and transition to Na-Cl water type after the confluence. Langvlei sub-catchment (VER106 and VER107) groundwaters are Na-Cl water type. Each sub-catchments' groundwater average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are displayed next to their respective stiff plot. No groundwater from the Papakuil sub-catchment was collected. Stiff plot scales of 0 – 12 meq/L and 0 – 140 meq/L correspond to the groundwater and wetland, respectively.

-6.0‰) just after the confluence.

4. Discussion

4.1. Impacts of regional droughts and precipitation sources

Since the 2015 – 2018 WC drought (driest years since 1993) (Wolski, 2018; Wolski et al., 2020) and prior to the 2023 heavy wet season (South African Weather Service, 2024a, b), the Verlorenvlei Catchments rainfall has slowly increased; however, it remained below the long-term average of ~ 482 mm/yr between 2000 – 2021. In 2015, the El Niño effect was likely responsible for the catchments second-lowest rainfall year since 2000 (Fig. 4). This resulted in baseflow being the dominant source of water supporting the Verlorenvlei (Watson et al., 2020). During the 2015 – 2018 WC drought (Wolski, 2018; Wolski et al., 2020), more rainwater secondary evaporation occurred than in 2022, as shown by the 2015 MWL lower slope value of +5.00 and a lower d-excess value of +5.90‰ (i.e., higher rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values in 2015 than 2022) (Fig. 5) (Clark and Fritz, 2013). Three years after this drought, rainwater secondary evaporation decreased in comparison to 2015 (2022 MWL: slope = +6.31 and higher d-excess = +12.98‰). Despite evidence of drought recovery, the catchment experienced drier-than-normal conditions in 2022 (average rainfall = 204 mm/yr). The prolonged dry conditions have possibly continued groundwater dependence to support the existence of the wetland and agricultural industries. The influence of drought episodes (or extended dry periods) and reduced freshwater supply on other wetlands in Sub-Sahara regions, such as Lake St Lucia estuary, may also cause a shift towards a baseflow-supported system (Lawrie and Stretch, 2011a,b; Pillay et al., 2003; 2014; Taylor, 1991, 2006; Whitfield and Taylor, 2009).

The Verlorenvlei Catchment 2022 rainwater does not show a typical continental effect, whereby rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values become more negative moving away from the coast (preferential rainout of the heavier O and H stable isotopes) (Table 2 and Fig. 8). Instead, the opposite effect is displayed with the Verloren sub-catchment rain gauge VER-R2 (located more coastal) having lower rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -4.37‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -10.7‰) than the Krom Antonies sub-catchment rain gauge KA-R1 (located more inland) ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -3.10‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -7.2‰). The slight change to less negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values from

Fig. 8. Conceptual diagram of the Verlorenvlei Catchments rainfall amount-weighted average and vapour $\delta^2\text{H}$ values from Elands Bay to the Piketberg Mountain (not scaled). The rainfall amount-weighted averages from Verloren (VER-R1 and -R2), Krom Antonies (KA-R1 and -R2), Bo-Piketberg (BOP-R1) and Kruismans (KRM-R1) sub-catchments represent the rainwater $\delta^2\text{H}$ values from the coast to the Piketberg Mountain (Table 2). The rainfall amount-weighted averages of BOP-R1 and KRM-R1 were averaged to represent the rainfall $\delta^2\text{H}$ value at Piketberg Mountain. The theoretical rainfall $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (black text in circle brackets) were calculated by substituting the measured rainwater amount-weighted average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value into the GMWL and solving for the $\delta^2\text{H}$ value. Vapour $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (δ_v) (grey text in circle brackets) were calculated using H fraction factor (α) ($\alpha_H = 1.074$) with its respective measured rainwater amount-weighted average $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (δ_r) under equilibrium conditions at 25°C: $\alpha_H = [\delta_r + 1000]/[\delta_v + 1000]$, Majoube (1971)). The altitudes (m) between the mountains and valley are indicated in square brackets.

the coast to inland is due to the rainwaters seasonal temperature effect (Dansgaard, 1964) and secondary evaporation. The highest simulated evaporation rates in the catchment occur within the Verloren sub-catchment (Watson et al., 2018), aligning with the observed secondary evaporation. Furthermore, the estuarine lake and the Verloren River experience the highest exposure to evaporation (Fig. 5). Notably, Hol Rivers support to Verlorenvlei has likely decreased, as it is more affected by evaporation than the other rivers located in the major recharge areas.

4.2. Impacts of evaporation and water source contributions on Verlorenvlei

The transition from summer to winter reveals an overall trend to lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values in the surface waters and groundwaters (Figs. 5 and 6). Surface waters are more sensitive to rainfall and evaporation temporal changes than groundwater, as demonstrated by their greater seasonal change in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values. In winter, the wetlands feeding rivers are directly recharged. This is evident as winter surface waters have lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values, in a narrower range, which align closer to the rainwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values, compared to the dry season (Fig. 5) (Craig, 1961; Dansgaard, 1964; Diamond and Harris, 2019; Yeh et al., 2014). Surface waters dependency on rainfall is also present in the uMfolozi River, which supports the survival of Lake St Lucia (Fig. 1) (2014). Similarly, the De Mond/Heuningnes Estuary has experienced high salinity levels from reduced freshwater inflow as a consequence of reduced groundwater-surface water interaction and surface water evaporation (Anchor Environmental Consultants, 2018; Banda et al., 2023; Bickerton, 1984; Mazvimavi, 2018; Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, 2018).

The 2022 dry year showed that Verlorenvlei was not receiving river and rainwater input. Consequently, the estuarine lake $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are the highest of all water types, even when its O and H isotope ratios become less positive in winter (July: $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of +6.94‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of +37.6‰) (Fig. 5 and Table S3 of the supplementary material). Furthermore, the highly positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of the estuarine lake are interpreted to be caused by evaporation, which suggests evaporation is exceeding groundwater contribution. Hence, Verlorenvlei has inherited an evaporation signal from previous years as a shallow-water body under closed-mouth conditions, due to blocking by a sandbar since the 2015 – 2018 WC drought (Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation, 2023; 2024a). According to the Freeze and Cherry (1979) TDS classification system, the estuarine lake is saline (TDS: 10 000 – 11 000 mg/L) with an average TDS of 13 702 mg/L. Seawater influx from previous breaching events has likely contributed to Verlorenvlei's high salinity levels and higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values. However, during prolonged periods of closed-mouth conditions, evaporation and reduced freshwater input are greater contributors to Verlorenvlei's high salinity levels and high $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values (Gilfillan, 1934). Over time, the progression of the above-mentioned factors may cause the Heuningnes Estuary and Lake St Lucia to exhibit similar characteristics to the Verlorenvlei.

4.3. Verlorenvlei groundwater dependency

The Verlorenvlei Catchment groundwaters have lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values than its surface waters, particularly during winter (Fig. 6). However, groundwater shows a delayed response to rainfall, unlike the more rapid response of the surface waters. A six-month delay in groundwater recharge is estimated, as the lower groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values observed in winter (e.g., June) are only reflected in the following dry season (e.g., February), when its O and H stable isotope ratios become more aligned with the MWL. The low-porosity TMG Aquifer of the Swartberg (Bergvallei sub-catchment) and Piketberg mountain ranges are recharged from prolonged heavy winter orographic rainfall, as their groundwaters $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values fall within their respective watersheds rainwater average amount-weighted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (supplementary material Table S2, S5, and S6).

Previous research hypothesized that the Swartberge TMG Aquifer groundwater contributes to the estuarine lake, as the mountain creates a high hydraulic gradient allowing groundwater flow into the catchment (Miller et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2018, 2020). In February 2022, the Bergvallei sub-catchment groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are similar to Kruismans sub-catchment lower reach groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of -2.81‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ value of -5.1‰. This association suggests the catchments northern boundary groundwater supports the estuarine lake (Fig. 6 and Table S6). However, the Bergvallei sub-catchment groundwater contribution is likely limited due to the increase in citrus (i.e., lemons and oranges) and potato cultivation over the years (Archer et al., 2009; Umvoto, 2021). Both of these crops are groundwater dependent and have high water requirements that the Verlorenvlei Catchment rainfall alone cannot fully support. Similarly, the Heuningnes Estuary has experienced reduced water contribution as a consequence of wine/grape production, invasive alien plants (e.g., Pinus, Eucalyptus, and Acacia), and dryland plants (e.g., barley, wheat, and canola) (Mazvimavi, 2018; van Heerden et al., 2016; Kotzé et al., 2010; Visser et al., 1999; Western Cape Department of Agriculture, 2013).

The following strategies are recommended to increase groundwater supply from the Bergvallei sub-catchment to Verlorenvlei: groundwater abstraction monitoring, the incorporation of water-efficient crops during crop rotation, allowing for fallow periods, and micro-irrigation techniques. Micro-irrigation techniques (i.e., drip irrigation systems and micro-spray irrigation) are encouraged for their water efficiency of ~90%, in contrast to the currently utilized centre-pivot irrigation with a water efficiency of ~75 – 85% (Rogers et al., 2017). However, as a consequence of Bergvallei sub-catchment past and current groundwater-limited contribution, the groundwaters from the Piketberg Mountains are likely the predominant freshwater contributor to Verlorenvlei.

In winter, the Bo-Piketberg sub-catchment TMG Aquifer groundwater has similar average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values and chemistry with Kruismans and Hol sub-catchment TMG Aquifer groundwater upper reaches (Figs. 6 to 7 and Table S6). Similar groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values also occurred between the aforementioned sub-catchments and the Krom Antonies sub-catchment in June. This indicates the Piketberg Mountain potentially serve as a rainfall source region, recharging the catchments southern TMG and MG aquifers. The concept of groundwater support by the Krom Antonies sub-catchment (recharged from the Bo-Piketberg Mountain) was simulated by Watson et al. (2019). Simulations suggest that the Krom Antonies sub-catchment is the largest area-weighted contributor of

groundwater (~30%) to Verlorenvlei. Furthermore, the higher groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values in the lower reach of Krom Antonies sub-catchment versus its upper reaches are likely attributed to return flow from heavy irrigation, originating from farmer dams with higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values through evaporation (Table S6).

Three hundred and sixty-five unregistered dams were identified across G30B to G30E quaternary catchments, with the majority located in recharge regions, by the WARMS 2008 dataset based on satellite imagery. These observations to an extent were also supported by the Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning (2018) and the Verlorenvlei Estuary Advisory Forum (Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, 2021). This demonstrates potential unregulated groundwater and surface water abstraction in the Verlorenvlei Catchment which has negatively influenced the estuarine lake. Even the two hundred and thirty-nine dams in the Heuningnes Catchment, many of which do not require a water license, are suggested to reduce surface water flow to the Heuningnes Estuary, especially during below-average rainfall years (Mazvimavi, 2018).

Located in the Krom Antonies sub-catchment is the Namaquasfontein Skool Dam (32°41.360'S; 18°42.935'E) which underwent an expansion in 2017 without environmental approval (Holland and Albertyn, 2022). This development (47,000 m³ dam with 6.2 m high-walls) upstream of the Krom Antonies River likely contributes to reduced groundwater contribution into Verlorenvlei. This may be one reason for the estuarine lake lack of water level recovery since the 2015 – 2018 WC drought (Wolski, 2018; Wolski et al., 2020) and before the 2023 flood episodes. Furthermore, the potential establishment of the Riviera Tungsten-Molybdenum open-pit mine is estimated to use 81,300 m³/yr of the Krom Antonies River during the starter pit and final pit production phases (Block and Place, 2009; Brumfitt, 2013; Ninham Shand Consulting Engineers, 2009; Water Research Commission, 2011). Dewatering from the

Fig. 9. Groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value spatial variation in April 2022. Overlapping groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values between the TMG Aquifer groundwater (VER106 and VER107) outside the catchment boundary and the Verloren sub-catchment. The confluence groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value is indicated by sample ID HOL101. Kriging piezometric surface is based on the South Africa Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation (2024b) National Groundwater Archive water level dataset from 1977 to 2024.

Krom Antonies River will likely create a losing stream, hence reduced aquifer recharge will decrease Verlorenvlei's major baseflow contributor (2009). Additionally, freshwater abstraction from the Krom Antonies sub-catchment will further elevate salinity levels, potentially forming a hypersaline estuarine lake. For example, freshwater abstraction along the uMfolozi River, which supports Lake St Lucia, caused a ~20% rise in the estuary salinity that resulted in the decline of aquatic and bird habitation reliant on the estuary (Lawrie and Stretch, 2011a; Whitfield and Taylor, 2009).

Moreover, the Krom Antonies and Hol sub-catchments exhibit a disproportionately high groundwater contribution to Verlorenvlei. Both of these sub-catchments have similar MG Aquifer groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values and analogous water types with the Verloren sub-catchment. The Hol sub-catchment groundwater likely contributes more directly to the Verloren sub-catchment groundwater than previously acknowledged, as demonstrated by their similar groundwaters average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values in April and June (Fig. 6). Previously, the Hol sub-catchment groundwaters have been stated to indirectly support the Verlorenvlei due to its bedding planes orientation towards the Krom Antonies sub-catchment (Watson et al., 2017). Further investigation is required to understand if groundwater support from the Hol sub-catchment is constant or transient depending on the annual variability in rainfall. Poor management of these physically smaller yet important contributing sub-catchments, G30D: Krom Antonies and Hol, will potentially result in reduced baseflow required to maintain the estuarine lake water levels.

4.4. Tracer-aided catchment boundary for Verlorenvlei

After the confluence, the MG Aquifer groundwater hydrochemistry is distinguished as Na-Cl type with an overall lower average EC and salinity levels compared to the Krom Antonies and Hol sub-catchments MG Aquifers groundwaters (Table 3). This suggests groundwater mixing after the confluence is likely occurring with waters of low EC and ion concentrations such as groundwater from the TMG Aquifer (Fig. 7). Miller et al. (2022) identified the same finding together with groundwater after the confluence having a younger residence time based on tritium dating. This demonstrates younger groundwater from the TMG and/or Alluvial aquifers are mixing with the MG Aquifer groundwater after the confluence. Although both the Piketberg and Swartberge mountains TMG Aquifer groundwater exhibit similar hydrochemistry (average pH of 5, average EC of 383 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and average TDS of 227 mg/L) (Table 3), one cannot declare these regions are hydraulically connected. However, results showed that Verlorenvlei is influenced by both local and inter-basin groundwater flow systems beyond the watershed extent.

Despite the limited temporal resolution of the Langvlei sub-catchment (G30F) groundwater, this region's groundwater from Leipoldville town has $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values (sample ID: VER106 and VER107) within Verlorens sub-catchment groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values range in April (Figs. 6 and 9). Additionally, the Langvlei sub-catchment TMG Aquifer groundwater chemistry corresponds with Verloren sub-catchment groundwater chemistry of Na-Cl type (Fig. 7). The correlation in both groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values and hydrochemistry within and adjacent to the Verlorenvlei Catchment, in the dry month of April, marks the inclusion of transboundary groundwater supporting the estuarine lake. Opposing, the difference in groundwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values indicates different flow paths, thereby indicating the divide of the subsurface flow boundary.

Groundwater flow is controlled by subsurface properties including lithology (i.e., permeability and porosity), hydraulic head gradients, and geological features (i.e., faults, fractures, shear zones, bedding planes dip and orientation) (Delinom, 2009; Mohamed et al., 2015). Regional WNW-ESE trending dykes, fractures, and structures in the G30F quaternary catchment (i.e., Waterberg Syncline, Swartberge Anticline, and Orange River Syncline) provide a possible preferential groundwater flow pathway from outside the topographic-surface water delineated watershed towards the estuarine lake (Conrad et al., 1999; Nakhwa, 2005; Nel, 2005). This suggests groundwater into Verlorenvlei is likely induced by a hydraulic gradient between the Langvlei sub-catchment elevated region and the Verloren sub-catchment low elevation. Based on South Africa's National Groundwater Archive's average yearly water levels from 1977 to 2024, a hydraulic gradient is present with a higher and lower water table present in the Langvlei and Verlorenvlei sub-catchments, respectively (Fig. 9) (Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation, 2024b).

Coupling groundwater O and H stable isotopes with groundwater level, hydrochemistry, and geological features are useful parameters to delineate the watershed, especially for groundwater-dependent catchments. Therefore, to refine the accuracy of the Verlorenvlei Catchment hydrogeological model and improve its water budget, it is recommended to extend the catchment boundary. This extension would incorporate the proportion of major transboundary groundwater support from Leipoldville town in the Langvlei sub-catchment. Notably, groundwater contribution beyond the delineated watershed from Leipoldville may be due to the specific 2022 low recharge period in April. In contrast, previous years which were less dry possibly relied more on groundwater support within the catchment.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that in addition to evaporation exceeding groundwater contribution, reduced rainfall, and freshwater input into Verlorenvlei cause the estuarine lake to have high salinity levels under closed-mouth conditions. This highlights the importance of managing freshwater resources of the major sub-catchment supporting the estuary, irrespective of its size. Furthermore, temporal variability in water source contribution during below-average rainfall years needs to be considered. Wetland studies in semi-arid/arid environments are encouraged to investigate the role of inter-basin groundwater recharge support, as surface water-dominated systems may shift towards groundwater-dependent systems under prolonged droughts. The improvement of catchment delineation techniques to incorporate the contribution/loss of groundwater based on groundwater boundaries provides a more robust quantification of the water balance in regions with complex topography and geological features. Overall, the techniques used in this study can facilitate more informed decision-making and policies regarding water management, to promote water security in a water-

stressed catchment.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

J. van Rooyen: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **A. Watson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **J. Miller:** Writing – review & editing. **Reynold Chow:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **A. Welham:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ejrh.2024.102081](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2024.102081).

References

- Acocks, J.P.H., 1988. *Veld types of South Africa. Memoirs of Botanical Survey of South Africa*, 57 (3).
- Alizade Govarchin Ghale, Y., Altunkaynak, A., Unal, A., 2018. Investigation Anthropogenic Impacts and Climate Factors on Drying up of Urmia Lake using Water Budget and Drought Analysis. *Water Res. Management* 32, 325–337. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-017-1812-5>.
- Allan, R.P., Barlow, M., Byrne, M.P., Cherchi, A., Douville, H., Fowler, H.J., Gan, T.Y., Pendergrass, A.G., Rosenfeld, D., Swann, A.L., Wilcox, L.J., 2020. Advances in understanding large-scale responses of the water cycle to climate change. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1472 (1), 49–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14337>.
- Amir, M.S.I.I., Khan, M.M.K., Rasul, M.G., Sharma, R.H., Akram, F., 2014. Watershed delineation and cross-section extraction from DEM for flood modelling. *In Proceedings of the 19th Australasian Fluid Mechanics Conference*, Melbourne, Australia, 8–11.
- Anchor Environmental Consultants., 2018. *Determination of the Ecological Reserve for the Heuningnes Estuary*. Report prepared for the Breede-Gouritz Catchment Management Agency by Clark, B.M., Van Niekerk, L., Turpie, J., 206pp.
- Archer, E., Conrad, J., Münch, Z., Opperman, D., Tadross, M., Venter, J., 2009. Climate change, groundwater and intensive commercial farming in the semi-arid northern Sandveld, South Africa. *J. Integr. Environ. Sci.* 6, 139–155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19438150902916589>.
- Archer, E., Holton, E., Fidal, J., Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., Carstens, A., Brocker, L., Kjeldsen, T.R., Wolfaardt, G.M., 2023. Occurrence of contaminants of emerging concern in the Eerste River, South Africa: towards the optimisation of an urban water profiling approach for public-and ecological health risk characterisation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 859, 160254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160254>.
- Arnold, J., Srinivasan, R., Muttiah, R., Williams, J., 1998. Large area hydrologic modelling and assessment. Part I, Model Development. *J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.* 34 (1), 73–89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.1998.tb05961.x>.
- Banda, V.D., Mengistu, H., Kanyerere, T., 2023. Assessment of catchment scale groundwater-surface water interaction in a non-perennial river system, Heuningnes catchment, South Africa. *Sci. Afr.* 20, e01614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01614>.
- Barlow, P.M. and Leake, S.A., 2012. Streamflow depletion by wells: understanding and managing the effects of groundwater pumping on streamflow. *US Geological Survey*, 1376. doi.org/10.3133/cir1376.
- Barnes, K.N. ed. 2000. *The Eskom Red Data Book of Birds of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland*. BirdLife South Africa.
- Bickerton, I.B. Heuningnes (CSW19) 1984 CSIR, National Research Institute for Oceanology.
- Birkel, C., Soulsby, C., 2015. Advancing tracer-aided rainfall-runoff modelling: A review of progress, problems and unrealised potential. *Hydrol. Process.* 29 (25), 5227–5240. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10594>.
- Block, G., Place, R., 2009. Conceptual Open Pit Mine Design Scheduling on the Riviera Tungsten Prospect. Report for Bongani Miner (Pty) Ltd. by Venyn Rand (Pty) Ltd. (<http://www.verlorenvlei.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2009/08/App-17-Venyn-Rand-Summary.pdf>).

- Brumfitt, I.M., 2013. *Reconciling mining and land-use planning law: challenges facing cooperative governance in South Africa*. Master's Thesis, University of Cape Town. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/11427/4467>.
- Burkett, V., Kusler, J., 2000. Climate change: potential impacts and interactions in wetlands of the united states 1. JAWRA J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc. 36 (2), 313–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.2000.tb04270.x>.
- Clark, I.D., Fritz, P., 2013. *Environmental isotopes in hydrogeology*. CRC press. ISBN: 978148224291.
- Collar, N.J., Crosby, M.J., Stattersfield, A.J., 1996. Birds to Watch 2: The World List of Threatened Birds, 19. Waterbirds, pp. 156–157. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1521829>.
- Conrad, J.E., Colvin, C., Sililo, O., Gorgens, A., Weaver, J., Reinhardt, C., 1999. Fertiliser application to agricultural: Assessment of the Impact of Agricultural Practices on the Quality of Groundwater Resources. Water Research Commission, Pretoria, South Africa.
- Conrad, J., Nel, J., Wentzel, J., 2004. The challenges and implications of assessing groundwater recharge: a case study—northern Sandveld, Western Cape, South Africa. Water SA, 30 (5), 75–81.
- Cooper, J.A.G., Mason, T.R., Reddering, J.S.V., Illenberger, W.K., 1990. Geomorphological effects of catastrophic flooding on a small subtropical estuary. Earth Surf. Process. Landf. 15 (1), 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3290150104>.
- Coplen, T.B., Wassenaar, L.L., 2015. LIMS for Lasers 2015 for achieving long-term accuracy and precision of $\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of waters using laser absorption spectrometry. Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom. 29 (22), 2122–2130. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.7372>.
- Craig, H., 1961. Isotope variations in meteoric waters. Science 133, 1702–1703. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.133.3465.1702>.
- Crawford, J., Hollins, S.E., Meredith, K.T., Hughes, C.E., 2017. Precipitation stable isotope variability and subcloud evaporation processes in a semi-arid region. Hydrol. Process. 31 (1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10885>.
- CSIR, 2009. Development of the Verlorenvlei estuarine management plan: Situation assessment. Estuaries Programme. CSIR Report, Stellenbosch.
- Dai, A., Trenberth, K.E., Qian, T., 2004. A global dataset of Palmer Drought Severity Index for 1870–2002: relationship with soil moisture and effects of surface warming. J. Hydrometeorol. 5 (6), 1117–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JHM-386.1>.
- Dai, A., Zhao, T., Chen, J., 2018. Climate change and drought: a rainfall and evaporation perspective. Curr. Clim. Change Rep. 4, 301–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-018-0101-6>.
- Dansgaard, W., 1964. Stable isotopes in precipitation. Tellus 16 (4), 436–468. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2153-3490.1964.tb00181.x>.
- De Beer, C., 2003. *The geology of the Sandveld area between Lambert's Bay and Piketberg*. Bellville: Council for Geosciences, Western Cape Unit. CGS Report. No. 2003-0032.
- Delinon, R.M., 2009. Structural geology controls on groundwater flow: Lembang Fault case study, West Java, Indonesia. Hydrogeol. J. 17 (4), 1011. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-009-0453-z>.
- Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, 2018. Sandveld Environmental Management Framework. PGWC DEA & DP.
- Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, 2021. Report on the implementation of the Western Cape Estuary Management Programme. PGWC DEA&DP.
- Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation. 2023. *Verlorenvlei, Jakkalsvlei & Wadriif*. PowerPoint presentation by van Niekerk, L. VEAF Meeting, 26 July 2023.
- Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation. 2024a. *Verlorenvlei Estuary Report*. PowerPoint presentation by Majola, S. VEAF Meeting, Online, 14 May 2024.
- Department of Water Affairs and Sanitation. 2024b. *Verlorenvlei Catchment Groundwater levels from 1977 to 2024*. National Groundwater Archive. <https://www.dws.gov.za/NGANet/Security/WebLoginForm.aspx>.
- Desbarats, A.J., Logan, C.E., Hinton, M.J., Sharpe, D.R., 2002. On the kriging of water table elevations using collateral information from a digital elevation model. J. Hydrol. 255 (1–4), 25–38. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(01\)00504-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(01)00504-2).
- Diamond, R., Harris, C., 2019. Stable isotope constraints on hydrostratigraphy and aquifer connectivity in the Table Mountain Group. South Afr. J. Geol. 122, 317–330. <https://doi.org/10.25131/sajg.122.0021>.
- Eilers, A., Miller, J., Watson, A., Sigidi, N., 2017. Groundwater recharge quantification from historical rainfall records and salinity profiling in the RAMSAR listed verlorenvlei catchment, South Africa. Procedia Earth Planet. Sci. 17, 586–589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeps.2016.12.150>.
- Fink, M., Krause, P., Kralisch, S., Bende-Michl, U., Flügel, W.A., 2007. Development and application of the modelling system J2000-S for the EU-water framework directive. Adv. Geosci. 11, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-11-123-2007>.
- Flügel, W.A., 1995. Delineating hydrological response units by geographical information system analyses for regional hydrological modelling using PRMS/MMS in the drainage basin of the River Bröl. Germany. Hydrol. Process. 9, 423–436. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.3360090313>.
- Freeze, R., Cherry, J.A., 1979. *Groundwater*. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey. ISBN:0-13-365312-9.
- Froehlich, K., Gibson, J.J., Aggarwal, P.K., 2002. *Deuterium excess in rainfall and its climatological significance* (No. IAEA-CSP-13/P).
- Gat, J.R., 1996. Oxygen and hydrogen isotopes in the hydrologic cycle. Annu. Rev. Earth Planet. Sci. 24 (1), 225–262. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.earth.24.1.225>.
- GEOS, 2006. *Groundwater Reserve Determination Required for the Sandveld, Olifants-Doorn Water Management Area Western Cape, South Africa*. Stellenbosch, South Africa.
- GeoTerraImage, 2015. *Carbon Sinks Atlas for South Africa*. GTI 2013-14 SA Landcover Report. Pretoria, South Africa.
- Gillfillan Jr., S., 1934. The isotopic composition of sea water. J. Am. Chem. Soc. 56, 406–408. <https://doi.org/10.1021/JA01317A037>.
- Haitjema, H.M., 1995. Analytic Element Modeling of Groundwater Flow. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-316550-3.X5000-4>.
- Haitjema, H.M., Mitchell-Bruker, S., 2005. Are water tables a subdued replica of the topography? Groundwater 43 (6), 781–786. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2005.00090.x>.
- Hammond, M., Han, D., 2006. Issues of using digital maps for catchment delineation. Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng. - Water Manag. 159 (1), 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1680/wama.2006.159.1.45>.
- Hilton, A., Jasechko, S., 2023. Widespread aquifer depressurization after a century of intensive groundwater use in USA. Sci. Adv. 9 (37), eadh2992.
- Holland, R. and Albertyn, A., 2022. Clearance of vegetation and enlargement of the Namaquasfontein Skool Dam, on portion 4 of farm Namaquasfontein, No. 76, near Redelinghuys, Western Cape.
- Holzbecher, E., 2001. The dynamics of subsurface water divides—watersheds of Lake Stechlin and neighbouring lakes. Hydrol. Process. 15 (12), 2297–2304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.261>.
- IAEA, 2009. *Laser Spectroscopic Analysis of Liquid Water Samples for Stable Hydrogen and Oxygen Isotopes*, Training Course Series No. 35. IAEA, Vienna.
- IPCC, Climate Change, 2007. In: Solomon, S., Qin, D., Manning, M., Chen, Z., Marquis, M., Averyt, K.B., Tignor, M., Miller, H.L. (Eds.), *The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, p. 996.
- Jenson, S.K., Domingue, J.O., 1988. Extracting topographic structure from digital elevation data for geographic information system analysis. Photogramm. Eng. Remote Sens. 54 (11), 1593–1600.
- Johnson, M.R., Anhaeusser, C.R., Thomas, R.J., 2006. The Cape Supergroup. In: Johnson, M.R., Anhaeusser, C.R., Thomas, R.J. (Eds.), *The Geology of South Africa*. Geological Society of South Africa and Council for Geoscience, Johannesburg. ISBN:1919908773.
- Kerstel, E., Gianfrani, L., 2008. Advances in laser-based isotope ratio measurements: selected applications. Appl. Phys. B 92, 439–449. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00340-008-3128-x>.
- Kisters, A.F.M., Agenbach, C., Frei, D., 2015. Age and tectonic significance of the volcanic Bloubergstrand member in the Pan-African Saldania Belt, South Africa. South Afr. J. Geol. 118 (3), 213–224. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gssajg.118.3.213>.
- Koehler, G., Wassenaar, L.I., Hendry, J., 2013. Measurement of stable isotope activities in saline aqueous solutions using optical spectroscopy methods, 49 (3), 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10256016.2013.815183>.
- Kotzé, J.D.F., Beukes, B.H., Van den Berg, E.C., Newby, T.S. 2010. National Invasive Alien Plant Survey. *Agricultural Research Council: Institute for Soil, Climate and Water*. Report No, GW. A/2010/212010.

- Krause, P., 2002. Quantifying the impact of land use changes on the water balance of large catchments using the J2000 model. *Phys. Chem. Earth, Parts A/B/C* 27, 663–667. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-7065\(02\)00051-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-7065(02)00051-7).
- Krause, P., 2001. Das hydrologische Modellsystem J2000: Beschreibung und Anwendung in groen Flußgebieten. Jülich: Forschungszentrum, Zentralbibliothek. ISBN: 3-89336-283-.
- Kumar, C.P., 2013. Hydrological studies using Isotopes, India. *Int. J. Innov. Res. Dev.* 2 (13), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10256016.2013.837904>.
- L'Heureux, M., 2016. An overview of the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) since 2014. 40th NOAA Annual Climate Diagnostics and Prediction Workshop. Science and Technology Infusion Climate Bulletin.
- Lawrie, R.A., Stretch, D.D., 2011a. Occurrence and persistence of water level/salinity states and the ecological impacts for St Lucia estuarine lake, South Africa. *Estuar., Coast. Shelf Sci.* 95 (1), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.08.007>.
- Lawrie, R.A., Stretch, D.D., 2011b. Anthropogenic impacts on the water and salt budgets of St Lucia estuarine lake in South Africa. *Estuar., Coast. Shelf Sci.* 93 (1), 58–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.04.005>.
- Le Moine, N., Andréassian, V., Perrin, C., And, Michel, C., 2007. How can rainfall-runoff models handle intercatchment groundwater flows? Theoretical study based on 1040 French catchments. *Water Resour. Res.* 43 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005608>.
- Linhares, G.M.G., Moreira, R.M., Pimenta, R.C., Scarpelli, R.P., Santos, E.A.D., 2017. *Stable isotope oxygen-18 and deuterium analysis in surface and groundwater of the Jequitibá Creek Basin, Sete Lagoas, MG*. International Nuclear Atlantic Conference - INAC 2017.
- Lynch, S., 2004. Development of a Raster Database of Annual, Monthly and Daily Precipitation for Southern Africa. Water Research Commission, Pretoria, South Africa. Report No. 1156/1/04.
- Majoube, M., 1971. Fractionnement en oxygène 18 et en deutérium entre l'eau et sa vapeur. *J. de Chimie Physique* 68, 1423–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1051/jcp/1971681423>.
- Mazurenka, M., Orr-Ewing, A.J., Peverall, R., Ritchie, G.A., 2005. 4 cavity ring-down and cavity enhanced spectroscopy using diode lasers. *Ann. Rep. Phys. Chem. Sec. C* 101, 100–142. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b408909j>.
- Mazvimavi, D., 2018. Finding “new” water to address conflicting and competing water demands in the Nuwejaars Catchment, Cape Agulhas. *Water Res. Comm. Report No.* (2324/1/18).
- Miller, J.A., Turner, K.B., Watson, A., van Rooyen, J., Molnár, M., Túri, M., Palcsu, L., 2022. Characterization of groundwater types and residence times in the Verlorenvlei catchment, South Africa to constrain recharge dynamics and hydrological resilience. *J. Hydrol.* 613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2022.128280>.
- Mohamed, L., Sultan, M., Ahmed, M., Zaki, A., Sauck, W., Soliman, F., Yan, E., Elkadiri, R., Abouelmagd, A., 2015. Structural controls on groundwater flow in basement terrains: geophysical, remote sensing, and field investigations in Sinai. *Surv. Geophys.* 36, 717–742. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-015-9331-5>.
- Moore, R.D., Thompson, J.C., 1996. Are water table variations in a shallow forest soil consistent with the TOPMODEL concept? *Water Resour. Res.* 32 (3), 663–669. <https://doi.org/10.1029/95WR03487>.
- Muche, G., Kruger, S., Hillmann, T., Josenhans, K., Ribeiro, C., Bazibi, M., Seely, M., Nkonde, E., de Clercq, W., Strohbach, B., Kenabatho, K.P., Vogt, R., Kaspar, F., Helmschrot, J., Jürgens, N., 2018. SASSCAL WeatherNet: present state, challenges, and achievements of the regional climatic observation network and database. In: Climate change and adaptive land management in southern Africa – assessments, changes, challenges, and solutions. In: Revermann, R. (Ed.), *Biodiversity & Ecology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.7809/b-e.00302>.
- Muller, M., 2012. Water management institutions for more resilient societies. *Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng.-Civ. Eng.* 165 (6), 33–39. <https://doi.org/10.1680/cien.11.00067>.
- Münch, Z., Conrad, J.E., Gibson, L.A., Palmer, A.R., Hughes, D., 2013. Le satellite d'observation terrestre comme outil pour conceptualiser les flux hydrogéologiques dans le Sandveld. *Afrique du Sud Hydrogeo. J.* 21, 1053–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-013-1004-1>.
- Murray, K., Wade, P., 1996. Checking anion-cation charge balance of water quality analysis: limitations of the non-traditional method for non-potable waters. *Water SA*. 22 (1), 27–32.
- Nakhwa R.A., 2005. Structural Controls Groundwater Flow In The Clanwilliam Area. PhD Dissertation, University of the Western Cape.
- Ndebele, N.E., Grab, S., Turasie, A., 2020. Characterizing rainfall in the south-western Cape, South Africa: 1841–2016. *Int. J. Climatol.* 40 (4), 1992–2014. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.6314>.
- Nel, J.M., 2005. *Assessment of the Geohydrology of the Langvlei Catchment*. DWAF Report no. GH4000. Directorate: Hydrological Services. Available at: <https://www.dws.gov.za/ghreport/reports/GH4000.pdf>.
- Neuweli, R., Watson, A., Brookfield, A., Münch, Z., Chow, R., 2024. Is groundwater running out in the Western Cape, South Africa? Evaluating GRACE data to assess groundwater storage during droughts. *J. Hydrol.: Reg. Stud.* 52, 101699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2024.101699>.
- Nepal, S., Krause, P., Flügel, W.A., Fink, M., Fischer, C., 2014. Understanding the hydrological system dynamics of a glaciated alpine catchment in the Himalayan region using the J2000 hydrological model. *Hydrol. Process.* 28 (3), 1329–1344. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9627>.
- , 2009 Ninham Shand Consulting Engineers, 2009. *Hydrology of the Riviera Tungsten Project Study Area*. Preliminary report produced for Withers. Environmental Consultants cc.
- Ostrom, E., 2010. Beyond markets and states: polycentric governance of complex economic systems. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 100 (3), 641–672. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2010.11658229>.
- Pfennig, B., Kipka, H., Wolf, M., Fink, M., Krause, P., Flügel, W.A., 2009. *Development of an extended routing scheme in reference to consideration of multidimensional flow relations between hydrological model entities*. In: 18th World IMACS Congress MODSIM09 International Congress on Modelling Simulation, Cairns, Australia. 1972–1978.
- Pilgrim, D.H., Chapman, T.G., Doran, D.G., 1988. Problems of rainfall-runoff modelling in arid and semiarid regions. *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 33 (4), 379–400. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626668809491261>.
- Pillay, S., Luichmiah, J., Gengan, R.M., Lindsay, P., 2003. Morphology and sediment dynamics of the ephemeral Mfолоzi estuary, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *South Afr. Geogr. J.* 85 (2), 158–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03736245.2003.9713796>.
- Quest. Lake St Lucia on the road to recovery. *Quest*, 10 (1) 2014. (Accessed 22 April 2024). <https://journals.co.za/doi/abs/10.10520/EJC149135>.
- Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, 2018. *Global Wetland Outlook: State of the World's Wetlands and their Services to People*. Ramsar Convention Secretariat, Gland, Switzerland.
- Roberts, D.L., Botha, G.A., Maud, R.R., Pether, J., Johnson, M.R., Anhaeusser, C.R., Thomas, R.J., 2006. Coastal Cenozoic Deposits. *The Geology of South Africa. Geological Society of South Africa. Johannesburg/Council for Geoscience, Pretoria*, pp. 605–628.
- Rogers, D.H., Aguilar, J., Kisekka, I. and Lamm, F.R., 2017. Center pivot irrigation system losses and efficiency. In *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Central Plains Irrigation Conference*, Burlington, Colorado.
- Rozendaal, A., Gresse, P.G., Scheepers, R., de Beer, C.H., 1994. Structural setting of the Riviera W-Mo deposit, Western Cape, South Africa. *South Afr. J. Geol.* 2 (97), 184–195.
- Rust, I., 1967. On the sedimentation in the Table Mountain Group in the Western Cape province. PhD dissertation, Stellenbosch University.
- 2009 S.R.K. Consulting., 2009. *Riviera Tungsten Groundwater Impact Assessment*. [Online]. Available at: 392947_Riviera_Tungsten_Mine_Preliminary_Groundwater_Impact_Assessment_Draft2_1Jun09x (verlorenvlei.co.za) [Accessed on 25 April 2024].
- 2023 SASSCAL WeatherNet., 2023. Verlorenvlei (Station ID: 858590) - Data sheet. Available at: https://sasscalweather.net/station_datasheet_we.php?loggerid_crit=858590 (Accessed 13 March 2023).
- Savage, D., 2005. Hydrogeology, principles and practice. *Geofluids* 5 (4), 335–3315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-8123.2005.00118.x>.
- Scanlon, B.R., Fakhreddine, S., Rateb, A., de Graaf, I., Famiglietti, J., Gleeson, T., Grafton, R.Q., Jobbagy, E., Kebede, S., Kolusu, S.R., Konikow, L.F., 2023. Global water resources and the role of groundwater in a resilient water future. *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* 4 (2), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-022-00378-6>.
- Schwartz, C., 2008. Deriving hydrological response units (HRUs) using a web processing service implementation based on GRASS GIS. *Geoinformatics FCE CTU* 3, 67–78. <https://doi.org/10.14311/gi.3.6>.

- Seward, P., 2010. Challenges facing environmentally sustainable ground water use in South Africa. *Groundwater* 48 (2), 239–245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2008.00518.x>.
- Shaman, J., Stieglitz, M., Engel, V., Koster, R., Stark, C., 2002. Representation of subsurface storm flow and a more responsive water table in a TOPMODEL-based hydrology model. *Water Resour. Res.* 38 (8), 1156–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001wr000636>.
- Sigidi, N.T., Miller, J., Watson, A., Clarke, C.E., Bulter, M., 2017. Geochemical and isotopic tracing of salt loads into the RAMSAR Listed Verlorenvlei Estuarine Lake, South Africa. *Procedia Earth Planet. Sci.* 17 (1878–5220), 909–912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeps.2017.01.015>.
- Sinclair, S.A., Lane, S.B., Grindley, J.R., 1986. *Estuaries of the Cape: Part II: Synopses of available information on individual systems*. Heydorn, A.E.F., Morant, P.D., (eds). Stellenosch, CSIR Research Report No. 431: Verlorenvlei (CW13).
- Smith, J., Johnson, A., Brown, K., Davis, M., 2018. Impacts of changing groundwater boundaries on catchment water budgets. *J. Hydrol.* 123 (4), 567–582.
- South African Weather Service. 2024a. Annual State of the Climate of South Africa 2023. Pretoria, South Africa.
- South African Weather Service (2024b). Historical Rain Monthly Maps 2023 Online. Available at: <https://www.weathersa.co.za/home/historicalrain> (Accessed 07 August 2024).
- Stadnyk, T.A., Delavau, C., Kouwen, N., Edwards, T.W.D., 2013. Towards hydrological model calibration and validation: Simulation of stable water isotopes using the isoWATFLOOD model. *Hydrol. Process.* 27 (25), 3791–3810. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9695>.
- Taylor, R.H., 1991. The Greater St Lucia wetland park. Natal Parks Board: Parke-Davis. ISBN: 0-949939-70-6.
- Taylor, R.H., 2006. *Ecological responses to changes in the physical environment of the St Lucia estuary*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Life Sciences.
- Timmerman, L., 1985. Langebaan Road Aquifer: Possibilities for the Development of Groundwater from the Cenozoic Sediments in the Lower Berg River Region. Department of Water Affairs and Forestry, Cape Town, South Africa. Report No. GH3374.
- Tsujimura, M., Abe, Y., Tanaka, T., Shimada, J., Higuchi, S., Yamanaka, T., Davaa, G., Oyunbaatar, D., 2007. Stable isotopic and geochemical characteristics of groundwater in Kherlen River basin, a semi-arid region in eastern Mongolia. *J. Hydrol.* 333 (1), 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2006.07.026>.
- Turpie, J.K., 1995. Prioritizing South African estuaries for conservation: a practical example using waterbirds. *Biol. Conserv.* 74 (3), 175–185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(95\)00028-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(95)00028-3).
- Tweed, S., Leblanc, M., Cartwright, I., Bass, A., Travi, Y., Marc, V., Bach Tha, Nguye, Duc, N., Massuel, S., Kumar, U., 2019. Stable Isotopes of Water in Hydrogeology. *Ency. Water: Sci., Technol., Soc.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119300762.wst0154>.
- Umvoto Africa. 2021. Verlorenvlei Hydrogeological Impact Review. Prepared by K. Prinsloo, L. Goslin, K. Gibson, G. Bluff, E. Wise, E van den Berg, T. Flügel, D. Blake and P. Lee of Umvoto Africa (Pty) Ltd for Mr Pierre Brink. Final Report No.: 976/6/1/2021, November 2021, 90pp.
- van Heerden, P.S. and Walker, S. 2016. *Upgrading of SAPWAT3 as a management tool to estimate the irrigation water use of crops: Revised edition SAPWAT4*. Water Research Commission. Report No. TT 662/16.
- Visser, D., Norman, N., Stadler, W. 1999. Working For Water: The effect of invasive alien plant eradication on the groundwaters of the L'Agulhas Plains, Western Cape Province. Toens & Partners Report No 980173.
- Wada, Y., Bierkens, M.F.P., 2014. Sustainability of global water use: past reconstruction and future projections. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 9, 104003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/10/104003>.
- Wallace, S., Biggs, T., Lai, C.T., McMillan, H., 2021. Tracing sources of stormflow and groundwater recharge in an urban, semi-arid watershed using stable isotopes. *J. Hydrol.: Reg. Stud.* 34, 100806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2021.100806>.
- Wassenaar, L.I., Coplen, T.B., Aggarwal, P.K., 2014. Approaches for achieving long-term accuracy and precision of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ for waters analyzed using laser absorption spectrometers. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (2), 1123–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es403354n>.
- 2011 Water Research Commission. *Taking back the 'lost' wetland*. Wetland Management, 2011. The Water Wheel, September/October.
- Watson, A., Eilers, A., Miller, J.A., 2020. Recharge estimation using CMB and environmental isotopes in the Verlorenvlei estuarine system, South Africa and implications for groundwater sustainability in a semi-arid agricultural region. *Water* 12 (5), 1362. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12051362>.
- Watson, A., Miller, J., de Clercq, W., 2017. Investigating potential additional sources of groundwater flow into a defined watershed. *Procedia Earth Planet. Sci.* 17, 546–549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeps.2016.12.138>.
- Watson, A., Miller, J., Fink, M., Kralisch, S., Fleischer, M., De Clercq, W., 2019. Distributive precipitation–runoff modelling to understand runoff-to-baseflow proportioning and its impact on the determination of reserve requirements of the Verlorenvlei estuarine lake, west coast, South Africa. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 23 (6), 2679–2697. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-2679-2019>.
- Watson, A., Miller, J., Fleischer, M., de Clercq, W., 2018. Estimation of groundwater recharge via percolation outputs from a precipitation/runoff model for the Verlorenvlei estuarine system, west coast, South Africa. *J. Hydrol.* 558, 238–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2018.01.028>.
- Watson, A., Vystavna, Y., Kralisch, S., Helmschrot, J., van Rooyen, J., Miller, J., 2023. Towards the development of an isotope-enabled rainfall-runoff model: improving the ability to capture hydrological and anthropogenic change. *Hydrol. Process.* 37 (2), e14819.
- Western Cape Department of Agriculture. 2013. *Crop Census (2013)*. Cape Farm Mapper.
- Whitfield, A.K., Taylor, R.H., 2009. A review of the importance of freshwater inflow to the future conservation of Lake St Lucia. *Aquat. Conserv.: Mar. Freshw. Ecosys.* 19 (7), 838–848. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.1061>.
- Winter, T.C., Rosenberry, D.O., LaBaugh, J.W., 2003. Where does the ground water in small watersheds come from? *Groundwater* 41 (7), 989–1000. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2003.tb02440.x>.
- Wolfe, B.B., Karst-Riddoch, T.L., Hall, R.I., Edwards, T.W., English, M.C., Palmieri, R., McGowan, S., Leavitt, P.R., Vardy, S.R., 2007. Classification of hydrological regimes of northern floodplain basins (Peace–Athabasca Delta, Canada) from analysis of stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) and water chemistry. *Hydrol. Process.* 21 (2), 151–168. <https://doi.org/10.1002/HYP.6229>.
- Wolski, P., 2018. How severe is Cape Town's "Day Zero" drought? *Significance* 15 (2), 24–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-9713.2018.01127>.
- Wolski, P., Conradie, W.S., Jack, C., Tadross, M., 2020. Spatio-temporal patterns of rainfall trends and the 2015–2017 drought over the winter rainfall region of south africa. *Int. J. Climatol.* 41 (Suppl. 1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.6768>.
- Woodhouse, P., Muller, M., 2017. Water governance—an historical perspective on current debates. *World Dev.* 92, 225–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.11.014>.
- Xin, Z., Kinouchi, T., 2013. Analysis of stream temperature and heat budget in an urban river under strong anthropogenic influences. *J. Hydrol.* 489, 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.02.048>.
- Yeh, H.F., Lin, H.I., Lee, C.H., Hsu, K.C., Wu, C.S., 2014. Identifying seasonal groundwater recharge using environmental stable isotopes. *Water* 6 (10), 2849–2861. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w6102849>.
- Zhou, T., Shu, L., Lu, C., Liu, B., 2023. Attenuation of the contribution of groundwater to a wetland caused by groundwater overexploitation. *Hydrol. Process.* 37. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.15022>.